

Proposed Methodology for Recognition of Plant Diseases by Leaf Image Classification Using Machine Learning

¹Prasad W. Bhombe, ²Dr. Shirish V. Patalwar

Abstract—Crop diseases are a noteworthy risk to sustenance security, however their quick distinguishing proof stays troublesome in numerous parts of the world because of the non-attendance of the important foundation. Emergence of accurate techniques in the field of leaf-based image classification has shown impressive results. This paper makes use of Random Forest in identifying between healthy and diseased leaf from the data sets created. Our proposed paper includes various phases of implementation namely dataset creation, feature extraction, training the classifier and classification. The created datasets of diseased and healthy leaves are collectively trained under Random Forest to classify the diseased and healthy images. For extracting features of an image, use Histogram of an Oriented Gradient (HOG). Overall, using machine learning to train the large data sets available publicly gives us a clear way to detect the disease present in plants in a colossal scale.

Keywords—Diseased and Healthy leaf, Random Forest, Feature Extraction, Training, Classification

I. INTRODUCTION

It is crucial to introduce technical improvement to domains related to crop productivity in nations like India. Increasing yield and food crop standards at cheap cost with a larger financial consequence is the goal of research endeavours and experimental study approaches in the crucial area of qualitative farming. The agricultural construction model exists as a result of a complex interaction between soil, seeds, and growth-promoting chemicals. Fruits and vegetables are currently one of the most important agricultural products produced. A product value assessment and improvement has always been critically significant in the directive for getting excess and worthwhile products.

Diseases impair a plant's normal state and prevent it from performing critical functions including transpiration, photosynthesis, fertilisation, pollination, germination, etc. Pathogens including fungus, bacteria, and viruses give rise to disease-distorting conditions as a result of undesirable

environmental conditions [8]-[9]. As a result, the initial step of plant disease diagnosis is a substantial responsibility. Farmers require expert monitoring on a regular basis, but this may be expensive and time-consuming [10]-[11]. Therefore, it is of utmost practical necessity to hunt for quick, less expensive, and accurate approaches to intelligently detect diseases from the symptoms that appear to be on the plant leaf.

In this work, we provide a method for determining the specific disease that an orange leaf might be carrying. By trying to implement socialization process technologies like image recognition [11], which represent the application functioning visually and is also a significant factor in increasing public awareness of digital technologies, it is of utmost importance to identify the type of disease an important crop like orange can have. Plant disease detection is done via machine learning. One of the components of artificial intelligence that works automatically or provides instructions to perform a certain task is machine learning.

Understanding training data and incorporating it into models that should be helpful to humans is the basic goal of machine learning. Therefore, plant disease detection via machine learning is possible [12].

The main issue in agriculture is that, because there are less natural resources, the yield grows according to the population growth. The main challenge here is to boost productivity in spite of unfavourable environmental factors. Precision agriculture is now a thing, and it makes use of the most cutting-edge technologies available to boost agricultural productivity. The automated leaf disease detection system, which is a part of the precision agriculture stream, uses computer vision, image processing, and machine learning algorithms to analyse photos of infected leaves to anticipate the spread of the illness [13].

The diagnosis procedure is sped up by the automatic disease detection system, which gives the farmer access to a quick and precise diagnosis of the plant illness. The farmer had to submit the diseased leaf to the pathology lab in the previous method, and the pathologist stated the illness. The main issue in agriculture is that, because there are less natural resources, the yield grows according to the population growth. The main issue here is to boost productivity in spite of unfavourable environmental factors. Precision agriculture is now a thing, and it makes use of the most cutting-edge technologies available to boost agricultural productivity.

The automated leaf disease detection method, that is a part of the precision agriculture sector, uses computer vision, image processing, and machine learning algorithms to

Manuscript Received July 15, 2022; Revised 16 August, 2022 and Published on September 01, 2022

Prasad W. Bhombe, Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering, Prof. Ram Meghe Institute of Technology and Research Badnera, Amravati, Maharashtra, India. Mail Id: prasadbhombel23@gmail.com

Dr. Shirish V. Patalwar, Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering, Prof. Ram Meghe Institute of Technology and Research Badnera, Amravati, Maharashtra, India. Mail Id: shirishpatalwar@rediffmail.com

analyse photos of infected leaves to anticipate the spread of the illness. The diagnosis procedure is sped up by the automatic disease detection technique, which gives the farmer access to a quick and precise diagnosis of the plant illness. In the prior method, the farmer was required to send the diseased leaf to a pathology lab where a pathologist confirmed the illness. This showed to be a labor-intensive task. Crop productivity is low as a result of a delayed reaction. For a quicker diagnosis of the crop, it is crucial to automate the disease detection approach.

The main issue in agriculture is that, because there are less natural resources, the yield grows according to the population growth. The main challenge here is to boost productivity in spite of unfavourable environmental factors. Precision agriculture has been developed recently and employs the most recent advances in agricultural technology to boost productivity. The automatic leaf disease detection system, which is a part of the precision agriculture stream, uses computer vision, image processing, and machine learning algorithms to analyse photos of infected leaves to anticipate the spread of the illness [14].

The diagnosis procedure is sped up by the automated disease detection system, that gives the farmer access to a quick and precise diagnosis of the plant illness. In the prior method, the farmer was required to send the diseased leaf to a pathology lab where a pathologist confirmed the illness. This showed to be a labor-intensive task. Crop productivity is low as a result of a delayed reaction. For a quicker diagnosis of the crop, it is crucial to automate the disease detection system. Earlier identification improves disease management, reduces pesticide usage and frequency, and increases crop output [15]-[16].

This study's main objectives are to design and create a better machine learning framework as well as to increase the classification accuracy of plant leaf disease and approaches. Particular goals are created in order to accomplish this research aim. The following elements make up the research goals of this study.

- Create innovative pre-processing methods to enhance image quality and Region of Interest selection (ROI).
- The categorization of ROI images using a machine learning algorithm, as well as effectiveness of the classifier to determine classification performance, sensitivity, and specificity

II. RELATED WORK

In [1] presented a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture for plant leaf disease detection. The Plant Village Dataset, which includes 54,305 photos of 38 different classes of both healthy and diseased leaves, is used to train a CNN model. With several hyperparameters of the Cnn model, various observations were made, and the suggested architecture's disease classification accuracy reached up to

95.81%. The experiment's outcomes are comparable to those of other methods that have been documented in the research.

A Random Forest technique was put forth in [2] to use the generated data sets to distinguish between healthy and unhealthy leaves. The stages of implementations in suggested study are dataset construction, feature extraction, classifier training, and classification. To categorise the photos of sick and healthy leaves, the produced datasets of sick and healthy leaves are combined and trained using Random Forest. We utilise a Histogram of an Oriented Gradient to extract features from an image (HOG). Therefore, it clearly identifies the illness present in plants on a massive scale by utilising machine learning to train the vast data sets that are available publicly.

To determine the kind of sickness, [3] suggested four sequential steps. Pre-processing, leaf segmentation, feature extraction, and classification are the four steps. Image segmentation is employed during pre-processing to eliminate noise and to separate the leaf's diseased or affected areas. The k-nearest neighbours (KNN) algorithm, a directed, supervised, and sophisticated machine learning algorithm, is used to incorporate solutions for both classification and regression-related issues. The consumer is advised to have the treatment during the final stage. The diseases primarily have a negative impact on live plants.

In [4] proposed using 18,161 plain and segmented tomato leaf photos with a deep learning architecture based on a current cnn called Efficiency Net to identify tomato illnesses. For the segmentation of leaves, the effectiveness of the two segmentation algorithms U-net and Improved U-net is presented. A comparison of the models performance for binary classification (healthy and unhealthy leaves), six-class classification (healthy and different categories of diseased leaves), and ten-class classification (healthy and different categories of unhealthy leaves) is also provided. For the segmentation of leaf pictures, the modified U-net segmentation model demonstrated accuracy, IoU, and Dice scores of 98.66%, 98.5%, and 98.73%, respectively.

Deep convolutional networks were used to construct a model for recognising plant diseases based on categorization of leaf images, as suggested in the study [5]. A fresh approach to training and the approach taken to enable a quick and simple system implementation in practice. With the ability to distinguish between plant leaves and their surroundings, the developed system can identify 13 distinct types of plant illnesses from healthy leaves. This approach to identifying plant diseases has, as far as we know, never been put forth before. The entire process of putting this disease recognition model into practise, from obtaining photos to building a database, is comprehensively documented in this work and evaluated by agricultural professionals.

A machine learning algorithm for identifying plant diseases was suggested in [6]. One of the components of artificial intelligence that works automatically or provides instructions to perform a certain task is machine learning. Understanding training data and incorporating it into algorithms that should be helpful to people is the basic goal

of machine learning. Therefore, identify plant illnesses using machine intelligence. It has aided in making wise decisions and forecasting the vast amount of data generated. Classification is based on the color of the leaves, the severity of leaf damage, and the location of the ill plant leaf.

In [7] developed and built an algorithm for a real-time decision assistance system that is integrated with a camera sensor module. Additionally, the effectiveness of three machine learning methods, including the Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Extreme Learning Machine (ELM) with linear and polynomial kernels, was examined. The outcomes show that the extreme learning machine performs better than the adopted support vector machine classifier. Additionally, it is noted that the support vector machine with a polynomial kernel outperforms the other classifiers in terms of sensitivity. The built real-time hardware can detect several plant illnesses, making this work appear to be of high social relevance.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Machine learning techniques are used in this research together with the three machine learning methods for feature extraction and leaf detection. The emphasis is on feature extraction using MATLAB and image processing packages, as well as prediction using machine learning algorithms. The three components of implementation are as follows. Image pre-processing, feature extraction, and leaf disease diagnosis make up the first section. The MATLAB library's built-in algorithms are used to identify leaf disease. The area of interest and significant leaf disease traits are retrieved from the leaf once the disease has been identified. The detection of leaf diseases can be done using a variety of features.

Figure 1: Block diagram of Proposed System

Figure 1 depicts the whole operation of the approach that is being given. The model that is being described consists of the following series of processes.

A. Dataset Description

Getting orange leaf images of diseased leaves is a procedure known as image acquisition. We must gather images from a

live farm in order to construct an image database on our own. Using a digital camera, photographs are taken from the farm and converted into digital files so that digital image processing activities can be carried out. Three diseased and one healthy orange leaf tree are utilised in this system's investigation with the categorization of orange leaf disease using the standard benchmark dataset from Kaggle.

B. Image Preprocessing

frequently entails eliminating reflections, adjusting the intensity of the individual particle pictures, and masking certain areas of the image. The process of improving data images before computational processing is known as image preprocessing.

C. Image Segmentation

In order to transform the representation of the image into something more meaningful and understandable, a process known as image segmentation divides the digital image into its individual regions or objects. The extent of segmentation is dependent on the problem being solved; segmentation should finish after the application's items of interest have been separated.

Figure 2: Image Segmentation

D. Feature Extraction

Texture Features: The texture is a repeated pattern of information or arrangement of the structure at regular intervals. In a general sense, texture refers to the surface characteristics and appearance of an object given by the size, shape, density, arrangement, and proportion of its elementary parts. A basic stage to collecting such features through the texture analysis process is called texture feature extraction. Due to the signification of texture information, texture feature extraction is a key function in various image processing applications like remote sensing, medical imaging, and content-based image retrieval.

There are four major application domains related to texture analysis namely texture classification, segmentation, synthesis, and shape from texture. Texture classification

produces a classified output of the input image where each texture region is identified with the texture class it belongs. Texture segmentation makes a partition of an image into a set of disjoint regions based on texture properties so that each region is homogeneous with respect to certain texture characteristics.

GLCM: The basic of GLCM texture considers the relation between two neighboring pixels in one offset, as the second-order texture. The gray value relationships in a target are transformed into the co-occurrence matrix space by a given kernel mask such as 3 3, 5 5, 7 7, and so forth. In the transformation from the image space into the co-occurrence matrix space, the neighboring pixels in one or some of the eight defined directions can be used; normally, four directions such as 0°, 45°, 90°, and 135° are initially regarded, and its reverse direction (negative direction) can be also counted into account. It contains information about the positions of the pixels having similar gray level values.

Energy: Energy (E) can be defined as the measure of the extent of pixel pair repetitions. It measures the uniformity of an image. When pixels are very similar, the energy value will be large. It is defined in Equation as

$$E = \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} M^2(i, j)}$$

Contrast: The contrast (Con) is defined in Equation, is a measure of intensity of a pixel and its neighbor over the image. In the visual perception of the real world, contrast is determined by the difference in the color and brightness of the object and other objects within the same field of view.

$$Con = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} (i - j)^2 M(i, j)$$

Correlation: Correlation is a measure of gray level linear dependence between the pixels at the specified positions relative to each other. On behalf a perfectly positively or negative correlated image, the correlation value is 1 and -1. On behalf of constant image its value is NaN.

Range = [-1, 1] and the formula is

$$Cor = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} M(i, j) \frac{(i - \mu_i)(j - \mu_j)}{\sqrt{\sigma_i^2 \sigma_j^2}}$$

Homogeneity: Homogeneity is going by the name of HOM. It passes the value that calculates the tightness of distribution of the elements in the GLCM to the GLCM diagonal. For diagonal GLCM its value is 1 and its range is [0, 1]. Opposite of contrast weight is homogeneity weight values, with weight decreases exponentially loose from the diagonal. The weight

employed in contrast is $(i-j)^2$ and in homogeneity, it is $1/(i-j)^2$. The equation is

$$Cor = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} M(i, j) / R$$

E. Machine Learning Classification

Machine learning is a subset of artificial intelligence in the field of computer science that often uses statistical techniques to give computers the ability to "learn" (i.e., progressively improve performance on a specific task) with data, without being explicitly programmed.

Ensemble Bagging Classifier: Ensemble bagging classifier which mainly named as Random Forest Tree Bagger which is a supervised classification algorithm. As the name suggest, this algorithm creates the forest with a number of trees. In general, the more trees in the forest the more robust the forest looks like. In the same way in the random forest classifier, the higher the number of trees in the forest gives the high accuracy results.

Figure 3: Workflow of Proposed System

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

The proposed work is implemented on Intel CORE processor i5, 8GB RAM Laptop configuration and the operating system is Windows 10. MATLAB R2018b software was used to write the programming code in this we used Image processing, Statistics and Machine Learning toolbox, and Deep Learning toolbox.

Figure 4: Training accuracy score

Figure 5: Sample dataset of orange leaf to test model

Figure 6: Select and Input the orange leaf to test model

Figure 7: preprocessing

Figure 8: Segmented Image of Input image

Figure 9: Accuracy Score of the proposed model

A. Comparative Analysis

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of proposed method with existing Methods

Ref.	Classifiers	Accuracy in %
[17]	SVM	84%
[18]	SVM	93%
[19]	CNN	88%
[20]	Random Forest	93%
Proposed Method	Random Forest	97%

Table 1 shows the comparative analysis of proposed method with existing methods. It is found that proposed classifier gives the better result as compared to previous classifiers.

CONCLUSION

Several types of orange leaf, including green, healthy, black spot, and canker leaves, were collected for this study. The data base was created using the suggested methodology, and image pre-processing was used to detect errors in submitted images. Smooth images were calculated, background and image regions were detected, and the rgb2gray scale format was converted. A GLCM approach has been applied in research work and is used for feature extraction. The GLCM approach is used to recognise the distinctive or real characteristics of uploaded images and to gather the characteristics of sickness symptoms. The image is segmented using a morphological method. Depending on the GLCM techniques, Ensemble Bagging Classifier has been used to categorise the disease in orange leaf. The detection issue with the illness of orange leaf is addressed by the suggested approach. To improve the results of illness diagnosis, Ensemble Bagging Classifier is used in the research proposal phase along with GLCM and K Morphological method.

The suggested model's accuracy rate is 97.5%, and the Graphical User Interface system for computed consequences and accuracy is displayed in that figure. The proposed image processing concept can therefore be used to calculate and take into account orange leaf illnesses. The accuracy rate of the present method was used to determine its performance. The accuracy rate of the suggested method to enhance performance is calculated.

REFERENCES

[1] Trivedi J., Shammani Y., Gajjar R. (2020) Plant Leaf Disease Detection Using Machine Learning. In: Gupta S., Sarvaiya J. (eds) Emerging Technology Trends in Electronics, Communication, and Networking. ET2ECN 2020. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 1214. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-7219-7_2

[2] S. Ramesh et al., "Plant Disease Detection Using Machine Learning," 2018 International Conference on Design Innovations for 3Cs Compute Communicate Control (ICDI3C), 2018, pp. 41-45, DOI: 10.1109/ICDI3C.2018.00017.

[3] G. Geetha, S. Samundeswari, G. Saranya, K. Meenakshi, and M. Nithya, "Plant Leaf Disease Classification and Detection System Using Machine Learning", Journal of Physics: Conference Series 1712 (2020) 012012. IOP Publishing. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1712/1/012012,

[4] Chowdhury, M.E.H.; Rahman, T.; Khandakar, A.; Ayari, M.A.; Khan, A.U.; Khan, M.S.; Al-Emadi, N.; Reaz, M.B.I.; Islam, M.T.; Ali, S.H.M. Automatic and Reliable Leaf Disease Detection Using Deep Learning Techniques. Agri Engineering 2021, 3, 294–312. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriengineering3020020>

[5] Srdjan Sladojevic, Marko Arsenovic, Andras Andela, Dubravko Culibrk, and Darko Stefanovic, "Deep Neural Networks Based Recognition of Plant Diseases by Leaf Image Classification", Hindawi Publishing Corporation Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience Volume 2016, Article ID 3289801, 11 pages <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2016/3289801>

[6] Monalisa Saha, E. Sasikala. (2020). Identification of Plants leaf Diseases using Machine Learning Algorithms. International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, 29(9s), 2900 - 2910. Retrieved from <http://sersc.org/journals/index.php/IJAST/article/view/15512>

[7] Paramasivam Alagumariappan, Najumnissa Jamal Dewan, Gaughan Narasimhan Muthukrishnan, Bhaskar K. Bojji Raju, Ramzan Ali Arshad Bilal, and Vijayalakshmi Sankaran, "Intelligent Plant Disease Identification System Using Machine Learning", Eng. Proc. 2020, 2, 49; doi:10.3390/ecsa-7-08160

[8] Aliyu M. Abdu, Musa M. Mokji, Usman U. Sheikh, "Machine learning for plant disease detection: an investigative comparison between support vector machine and deep learning", IAES International Journal of Artificial Intelligence (IJ-AI), Vol. 9, No. 4, December 2020, pp. 670~683

[9] Ms. Nilam Bhise, Ms. Shreya Kathet, Mast. Sagar Jaiswar, Prof. Amarja Adgaonka, "Plant Disease Detection using Machine Learning", International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET), Volume: 07 Issue: 07, July 2020.

[10] Vijay Borate, Sheetal Patange, Vaibhav Vede, Onkar kale, "Plant Leaf Disease Detection Using Machine Learning", IJARIE, Vol-4 Issue-2 2018

[11] Chandra S.S., Vinod "Machine Learning A Practitioner's Approach" PHI Learning A. S. Tripathy and D. K. Sharma, "Image Processing Techniques Aiding Smart Agriculture," in Modern Techniques for Agricultural Disease Management and Crop Yield Prediction: IGI Global, pp. 23-48, 2020.

[12] P. S. Ojiambo, J. Yuen, F. van den Bosch, and L. V. Madden, "Epidemiology: Past, Present, and Future Impacts on Understanding Disease Dynamics and Improving Plant Disease Management-A Summary of Focus Issue Articles," Phytopathology, vol. 107, no. 10, pp. 1092-1094, 2017/10/01 2017.

[13] S. Kaur, S. Pandey, and S. Goel, "Plants Disease Identification and Classification Through Leaf Images: A Survey," Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering, journal article January 19 2018.

[14] Y. Fang and R. P. Ramasamy, "Current and Prospective Methods for Plant Disease Detection," (in eng), Biosensors, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 537-561, 2015.

[15] J. G. A. Barbedo, "A review on the main challenges in automatic plant disease identification based on visible range images," Biosystems Engineering, vol. 144, pp. 52-60, 2016.

[16] T. U. Rehman, M. S. Mahmud, Y. K. Chang, J. Jin, and J. Shin, "Current and future applications of statistical machine learning algorithms for agricultural machine vision systems," Computers and Electronics in Agriculture, vol. 156, pp. 585-605, 2019/01/01/ 2019.

[17] S. C. Madiwalar and M. V. Wyawahare, "Plant disease identification: A comparative study," 2017 International Conference on Data Management, Analytics and Innovation (ICDMAI), 2017, pp. 13-18, doi: 10.1109/ICDMAI.2017.8073478.

[18] 3. P. Moghadam, D. Ward, E. Goan, S. Jayawardena, P. Sikka and E. Hernandez, "Plant Disease Detection Using Hyperspectral Imaging," 2017 International Conference on Digital Image Computing: Techniques and Applications (DICTA), 2017, pp. 1-8, doi: 10.1109/DICTA.2017.8227476.

[19] 4. S. D.M., Akhilesh, S. A. Kumar, R. M.G. and P. C., "Image based Plant Disease Detection in Pomegranate Plant for Bacterial Blight," 2019 International Conference on Communication and Signal

Processing (ICCSP), 2019, pp. 0645-0649, doi:
10.1109/ICCSP.2019.8698007

[20] G. Shrestha, Deepshikha, M. Das and N. Dey, "Plant Disease Detection Using CNN," 2020 IEEE Applied Signal Processing Conference (ASPCON), 2020, pp. 109-113, doi:
10.1109/ASPCON49795.2020.9276722. 8.

[21] Prasad W. Bhombe, Dr. Shirish V. Pattalwar, "Comparative Study on Plant Leaf Disease Detection and Classification, Based on Machine

Learning Techniques", International Journal of Research in Computer & Information Technology (IJRCIT), Vol.7, Issue 2, March 2022.

[22] Prasad W. Bhombe, Dr. Shirish V. Pattalwar, "Implementation of plant diseases recognition by Image processing using Machine Learning", International Journal of Advanced Innovative Technology in Engineering, 2022, 7(3), PP 175-186..